

Steady aerodynamic and aeroacoustic optimization of an eVTOL rotor

Tyler R. Critchfield*

Brigham Young University, Provo, UT, 84602

Urban air mobility is an exciting and impactful technology that has the potential to revolutionize modern transportation. To effectively design such aircraft, aeroacoustic and aerodynamic effects need to be considered together to ensure a robust design that is aerodynamically efficient and quiet. This work models an eVTOL rotor using blade element momentum theory and PSU-WOPWOP, a commercially available acoustics solver. Using these models, the rotor is optimized using surrogate models and a gradient-based optimization with aerodynamic and acoustic constraints. The optimization was able to reduce noise considerably with only a 0.3% decrease in propulsive efficiency.

I. Nomenclature

a	=	speed of sound
a_x	=	tangential induction factor
a_y	=	circumferential induction factor
c	=	chord
C_Q	=	torque coefficient
C_T	=	thrust coefficient
δ_{ij}	=	dirac delta function
η_{prop}	=	propulsive efficiency
F	=	tip/hub loss factor
J	=	advance ratio
M_{tip}	=	Mach number at rotor tip
\hat{n}	=	unit normal to the blade surface
r	=	vector from the noise source to an observer
\hat{r}	=	unit vector from the noise source to an observer
Ω	=	rotational speed in rad/sec
p_0	=	reference pressure
p'	=	acoustic pressure
p'_L	=	acoustic pressure from loading source
p'_T	=	acoustic pressure from thickness source
ϕ	=	local inflow angle
ρ_0	=	ambient air density
ρ	=	local air density
σ'	=	local solidity
V_∞	=	freestream velocity

II. Introduction

The urban air mobility (UAM) concept is an intriguing look into the future of urban transportation. By using electric vertical takeoff and landing (eVTOL) aircraft, UAM can provide urban cities with efficient and pollution-free transportation without the need for long runways in airports far away from the population. Recent advances in battery technology and autonomous control navigation have made UAM a reality for the near future and a subject of interest to many researchers and companies. To effectively operate in dense, urban environments, these aircraft must be quiet or

*PhD Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering, AIAA Student Member.

risk annoying city inhabitants and communities. In addition, they need to be aerodynamically efficient to keep operating costs low and maximize range. Acoustic design considerations typically come at the expense of aerodynamic efficiency, so multi-disciplinary design and optimization is well-suited to solve this coupled problem and find designs that are both aerodynamically efficient and quiet.

Effective mitigation of noise pollution for eVTOL aircraft must begin with rotor design, which consists of blades that are moving very quickly through the air. If acoustic effects are not considered in their design, these rotors can become very noisy. Many research efforts have been made to increase aerodynamic efficiency and/or decrease noise pollution in eVTOL rotors. Some examples in the literature include using “stacked” or offset propellers [1, 2], ducted propellers [2, 3], and unsymmetrical or non-uniform blade spacing [4, 5]. Zolbayar [6] extensively investigated noise from low-tip-speed propellers by studying the effect of blade tip speed, unsteady loading, number of blades and rotors, hub radius, and lift coefficient on total sound pressure level. Passe [7] used computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to model aerodynamic loads and noise of eVTOL propellers of various geometries and loadings. While instructive, these studies did not incorporate an optimization framework to find optimal designs and to study more of the design space for eVTOL rotors. Ingraham et al. [8] developed a propeller optimization for NASA’s Maxwell X-57 electric plane with acoustic constraints and resulted in a 5 dB reduction in sound pressure level without a significant decrease in aerodynamic performance.

This work reflects preliminary efforts to model and optimize an eVTOL rotor with aerodynamic and acoustic considerations. Blade element momentum theory and PSU-WOPWOP are used together in conjunction with surrogate modeling techniques and a gradient-based constrained optimization to optimize the design of a single 3-bladed rotor in hover with and without a major acoustic constraint.

III. Methods

A. Blade Element Momentum Theory

The propeller aerodynamics are modeled using blade element momentum theory (BEMT). BEMT combines a momentum balance and airfoil analysis along the radius of the rotor blade. The momentum balance is performed on a streamtube which contains the rotor as well as upstream and downstream flow. The airfoil analysis is performed on various radial sections of the rotor blade, with each section acting as a 2D airfoil. Using the method described in [9], a solution can be found from combining these two analyses that is guaranteed to converge, which is very useful for design optimizations. Specifically, the following residual function results from equating thrust and torque equations predicted by the two theories:

$$\frac{\sin(\phi)}{1 + a_x} - \frac{V_\infty \cos(\phi)}{\Omega r(1 - a_y)} = 0 \quad (1)$$

a_x and a_y are the tangential and circumferential induction factors:

$$a_x = \frac{\sigma' c_n}{4F \sin^2(\phi) - \sigma' c_n} \quad (2)$$

$$a_y = \frac{\sigma' c_t}{4F \sin(\phi) \cos(\phi) - \sigma' c_t} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the local inflow angle, σ' is the local solidity, c_n is the normal force coefficient, c_t is the tangential force coefficient, and F is a tip/hub loss correction factor. This analysis yields thrust and power coefficients which can be used to calculate propulsive efficiency:

$$\eta_{\text{prop}} = \frac{J}{2\pi} \frac{C_T}{C_Q} \quad (4)$$

where J is the propeller advance ratio. In this present work I have assumed steady inflow conditions and no interactions between blade sections. While based on relatively straightforward physics principles, BEMT provides a robust and efficient way to model the aerodynamic performance of our rotor in this work.

B. Acoustics modeling

The aeroacoustics of a rotor are complex and can be difficult to model. Most acoustic solvers stem from the Ffowks-Williams Hawkins (FWH) equation [10], which is a rearrangement of the continuity and Navier-Stokes equations into a form of the wave equation. This method naturally results in three distinct noise source terms: monopole (thickness noise), dipole (loading noise), and quadrupole (high-speed impulsive noise) source terms. The latter is often neglected for subsonic rotors.

This work uses PSU-WOPWOP for acoustic analysis, software developed by Kenneth Brentner at Penn State University [11], which uses Farrassat's Formulation 1A [12] to solve the FWH equation:

$$p'(x, t) = p'_T(x, t) + p'_L(x, t) \quad (5)$$

where the thickness term is

$$4\pi p'_T(x, t) = \int_{f=0} \left[\frac{\rho_0(\dot{v}_n + v_{\dot{n}})}{r|1 - M_r|^2} \right]_{ret} dS + \int_{f=0} \left[\frac{\rho_0 v_n (r\dot{M}_r + aM_r - aM^2)}{r^2|1 - M_r|^3} \right]_{ret} dS \quad (6)$$

and the loading term is

$$4\pi p'_L(x, t) = \frac{1}{a} \int_{f=0} \left[\frac{\dot{l}_r}{r|1 - M_r|^2} \right]_{ret} dS + \int_{f=0} \left[\frac{l_r - l_M}{r|1 - M_r|^2} \right]_{ret} dS + \frac{1}{a} \int_{f=0} \left[\frac{l_r (r\dot{M}_r + aM_r - aM^2)}{r^2|1 - M_r|^3} \right]_{ret} dS \quad (7)$$

$l = (p - p_0)\delta_{ij}\hat{n}_j$, a is the speed of sound, and the $f = 0$ limit means the integrand is evaluated at the rotor surface. dS refers to a single rotor blade surface element. A dot over the variable refers to the source time derivative ($\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}$). Subscripts refer to the dot product with the respective variable (n , the unit normal vector; r , the unit radiation vector from the source to observer, and M , the surface mach number.) Terms with a $1/r$ dependence are far field terms and terms with a $1/r^2$ dependence are near-field terms.

These equations are solved by PSU-WOPWOP based on the rotor geometry, operating parameters, and loading. This software outputs sound pressure level for a wide-range of frequencies for each specified observer. Overall sound pressure level (OASPL) is essentially an integration of these pressures over all frequencies. This is the metric we use in this work to compare the acoustic effects of each design.

This approach has accuracy limitations as I have neglected some noise sources. Broadband noise, noise due to unsteady loading, and noise due to rotor-on-rotor and rotor-on-wing interactions are not captured in the current analysis.

C. Optimization Approach

A single 3-bladed propeller in hover with steady loading was optimized to maximize propulsive efficiency. Details of these optimization problems are given in the next section. These problems were optimized using a Julia wrapper to SNOPT* [13]. BEMT was called in conjunction with PSU-WOPWOP to solve for the coupled aerodynamics and aeroacoustics of the system.

This work optimizes the design of a rotor meant for eVTOL applications. The Vahana aircraft concept from Airbus [14] is a reasonable estimate for the requirements an eVTOL rotor may need to satisfy. The Vahana has a max takeoff weight of 815 kg and eight propellers. For a flight condition in hover-mode, each propeller would need to produce at least 1 kN of thrust to maintain altitude. For these problems, the rotors had a fixed number of blades (3), a rotor hub radius of 0.3 m, and a constant Eppler e63 airfoil.

With several design variables, I needed a gradient-based constrained optimization to find the optimal design in a computationally efficient manner. Without access to some of the source code used in the acoustic analysis, I could not obtain exact gradients for the OASPL constraint. To avoid using finite differencing methods, I instead created a surrogate model to predict the OASPL of each design. I also created surrogates for the thrust constraint and the efficiency objective. Surrogates are fast and relatively simple to implement; however, they are at best an estimate of the global function. To increase accuracy, I implemented infill over several optimization iterations. The rotor design was

*<https://github.com/byuflowlab/Snopt.jl>

(a) η_{prop}

(b) Thrust

(c) OASPL

Fig. 1 Kriging surrogate models for propulsive efficiency, thrust, and OASPL with respect to rotor radius and RPM. While difficult to see in a 2D rendering, all three model the system behavior relatively well with respect to these two variables.

optimized in a loop, and at each optimal design the real functions were called and added to the training set to re-train the surrogates. Despite inaccuracies in the global model, this method ensures greater accuracy near the optimal point while maintaining computational efficiency. The true optimum was considered reached when the optimal design was feasible and when the predicted values from the surrogates did not vary more than 1% of their true values. The objective, constraints, and design variables were scaled everywhere accordingly to ensure their gradients were of the same order of magnitude in the optimization.

I created these surrogates using the Surrogate Modeling Toolbox (SMT) [15]. This toolbox provides gradients for each surrogate at any specified point with respect to any variable, allowing the optimization to run completely gradient-based. Specifically, I implemented the Kriging partial least squares (KPLS) method with linear regression from training data created using a Latin hypercube approach. Figure 1 shows these three surrogate models with respect to the first two design variables: rotor radius and RPM. Blue dots represent training data used to create the surrogate and orange dots are predicted values of the model at randomly generated locations in the design space. With respect to these two design variables, all three surrogates appear to model the system behavior relatively well (this is before any infill occurred). The thrust model appears to lose accuracy at high RPM and high radius values. This is not a problem for these designs because that part of the design space is already infeasible due to a constraint on the rotor tip speed.

IV. Results/Discussion

The first optimization was performed without any constraints on the overall sound pressure level (OASPL). However, the OASPL was still calculated at an observer 20 m below the rotor to provide a reference value for the second optimization. Table 1 presents the objective, constraints, and design variables of this initial framework. Rotor radius and RPM, blade chord (for 10 blade sections) and blade twist (for 10 blade sections) were the chosen design variables. Constraints included a minimum thrust and a maximum Mach tip speed. As previously mentioned, I used the Vahana concept as a guide and determined that each rotor needed to produce at least 1 kN of thrust for this simplified scenario. The Mach tip speed constraint was chosen to reduce noise and to reduce the risk of shock waves at the blade tips. An upper bound of 0.4 is a common metric used in the literature [16, 17] for this purpose.

Table 1 First optimization framework with OASPL unconstrained.

	Variable	Lower	Upper
maximize	η_{prop}	-	-
with respect to	radius	0.5 m	2.0 m
	RPM	500 RPM	5000 RPM
	blade chord (10 sections)	5 cm	50 cm
	blade twist (10 sections)	20 deg	70 deg
subject to	M_{tip}	-	0.4
	Thrust	1000 N	-

Akima 1D splines[†] were used to interpolate the blade geometry (chord and twist) between the values denoted by the design variables. In a hover scenario, the advance ratio (and thus propulsive efficiency) approaches zero, so a small velocity was given to the system to still be able to compare and optimize the efficiency.

The resulting design is shown in Table 2 and Fig. 2. The optimizer went consistently to the lower bound for the RPM and increased the radius just enough to achieve enough thrust. The tip speed constraint was inactive.

Table 2 Optimal values with OASPL unconstrained.

	Optimal value
Radius	1.44945 m
RPM	500 RPM
η_{prop}	7.69×10^{-4}
M_{tip}	0.22
Thrust	1004.06 N
OASPL	21.71 dB

The resulting chord and twist distributions are not very clean nor intuitive to analyze, and could be a result of too many design variables along the rotor for the chord and twist.

A second optimization was then performed that included a maximum constraint on the OASPL for an observer 20 m below the rotor. This constraint was a reduction of 1 dB from the unconstrained OASPL value. Table 3 presents this framework.

Figure 3 and Table 4 show the results for this second optimization. Interestingly, the optimizer increased the radius slightly and increased the chord closer to the hub of the rotor. This second design resulted in constant twist along the blade at the lower bound of 20 deg.

[†]<https://github.com/byuflowlab/FLOWMath.jl>

Fig. 2 Chord and twist distributions for the unconstrained optimal rotor design.

Table 3 Second optimization framework with constrained OASPL.

	Variable	Lower	Upper
maximize	η_{prop}	-	-
with respect to	radius	0.5 m	2.0 m
	RPM	500 RPM	5000 RPM
	blade chord (10 sections)	5 cm	50 cm
	blade twist (10 sections)	20 deg	70 deg
subject to	M_{tip}	-	0.4
	Thrust	1000 N	-
	OASPL	-	OASPL ₀

Figure 4 shows the rotor performance of each of these designs using BEMT. These results highlight the shifting of the aerodynamic loads further away from the tip in the constrained case to reduce overall noise impact without a major loss in propulsive efficiency (0.3% for this case). This seems to suggest an effective strategy for reducing noise in eVTOL rotors is to shift the aerodynamic loads inward toward the parts of the blade that have a lower velocity, in addition to increasing the overall mass flow rate to maintain enough propulsive thrust.

Table 4 Optimal values with OASPL unconstrained.

	OASPL unconstrained	OASPL constrained
Radius	1.44945 m	1.63186 m
RPM	500 RPM	500 RPM
η_{prop}	7.69×10^{-4}	7.66×10^{-4}
M_{tip}	0.22	0.25
Thrust	1004.06 N	1004.71 N
OASPL	21.71 dB	20.64 dB

Fig. 3 Chord and twist distributions for the unconstrained and constrained optimal rotor designs.

Fig. 4 Chord and twist distributions for the unconstrained and constrained optimal rotor designs.

V. Conclusion

Aerodynamics and aeroacoustics of a single eVTOL rotor were modeled using blade element momentum theory and PSU-WOPWOP. The rotor was optimized using surrogate modeling techniques and gradient-based constrained optimization to maximize propulsive efficiency with aerodynamic and acoustic constraints. Two optimizations were

performed; the first had no major acoustic constraint while the second constrained the design to reduce the overall sound pressure level (OASPL) by 1 dB from the OASPL of the previous optimal design. To reduce noise, the optimizer shifted the distributed loads along the blade further in toward the hub and increased the radius just enough to maintain sufficient thrust, and did this with only a 0.3% drop in propulsive efficiency. While instructive, this work only scratches the surface of the coupled aerodynamics and aeroacoustic effects that need to be considered in eVTOL rotor design. Future work will build on this research by including more noise sources (such as broadband noise) and by increasing the fidelity of the aerodynamic models to include unsteady freestream inflow and unsteady loading on the rotor blades due to rotor-on-rotor interactions.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank Dr. Andrew Ning and Eduardo Alvarez for their helpful conversations and code development used in this work.

References

- [1] Rozhdestvensky, M. G., “Essential results obtained from research involved in scissors motors,” 1995.
- [2] Antcliff, K., Whiteside, S., Kohlman, L. W., and Silva, C., “Baseline Assumptions and Future Research Areas for Urban Air Mobility Vehicles,” *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, 2019, p. 0528. doi:10.2514/6.2019-0528.
- [3] Bogdanski, K., Krusz, W., Rodzewicz, M., and Rutkowski, M., “Design and Optimization of Low Speed Ducted Fan for a New Generation of Joined Wing Aircraft,” *29th Congress of the International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences*, 2014.
- [4] Dobrzynski, W., “Propeller Noise Reduction by Means of Unsymmetrical Blade-spacing,” *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 163, No. 1, 1993, pp. 123 – 126. doi:https://doi.org/10.1006/jsvi.1993.1152, URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022460X83711521>.
- [5] Floros, M. W., “Performance and Acoustics of Small Rotors with Non-Uniform Blade Spacing,” *Vertical Flight Society 75th Annual Forum Technology Display*, 2019.
- [6] Zolbayar, B. E., “Investigation Noise from Electric, Low-Tip-Speed Aircraft Propellers,” Master’s thesis, The Pennsylvania State University, 2018.
- [7] Passe, B., “Computational Aeroacoustics of Various Propeller Designs for eVTOL Applications,” Ph.D. thesis, University of Maryland, 2019.
- [8] Ingraham, D., Gray, J. S., and Lopes, L. V., “Gradient-Based Propeller Optimization with Acoustic Constraints,” *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, 2019, p. 1219.
- [9] Ning, S. A., “A simple solution method for the blade element momentum equations with guaranteed convergence,” *Wind Energy*, Vol. 17, No. 9, 2014, pp. 1327–1345.
- [10] Ffowcs Williams, J. E., and Hawkings, D. L., “Sound generation by turbulence and surfaces in arbitrary motion,” *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, Vol. 264, No. 1151, 1969, pp. 321–342.
- [11] Brentner, K. S., Bres, G. A., Perez, G., and Jones, H. E., “Maneuvering Rotorcraft Noise Prediction: A New Code for a New Problem,” Tech. rep., 2002.
- [12] Farassat, F., “Linear acoustic formulas for calculation of rotating blade noise,” *AIAA journal*, Vol. 19, No. 9, 1981, pp. 1122–1130.
- [13] Gill, P., Murray, W., and Saunders, M., “SNOPT: An SQP Algorithm for Large-Scale Constrained Optimization,” *SIAM Journal of Optimization*, Vol. 47, No. 1, 2007, pp. 99–131. doi:10.1137/S0036144504446096.
- [14] “A3 Vahana,” 2019. URL <https://evtol.news/aircraft/a3-by-airbus/>.
- [15] Bouhleb, M. A., Hwang, J. T., Bartoli, N., Lafage, R., Morlier, J., and Martins, J. R. R. A., “A Python surrogate modeling framework with derivatives,” *Advances in Engineering Software*, 2019, p. 102662. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2019.03.005.
- [16] Hwang, J., and Ning, A., “Large-scale multidisciplinary optimization of an electric aircraft for on-demand mobility,” *Journal of Aircraft*, 2018. (in review).

- [17] Moore, K. R., and Ning, A., *Distributed Electric Propulsion Effects on Existing Aircraft Through Multidisciplinary Optimization*, chapter and pages. doi:10.2514/6.2018-1652, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2018-1652>.